

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18215786>

INTEGRATING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN ELT: PEDAGOGICAL JUSTIFICATIONS AND EDUCATIONAL BENEFITS

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ABSTRACT

This article explores the importance of including innovative technologies in English classes. It not only provides a comprehensive literature review about the impact of newly developed technological tools on the teaching and learning process but also presents scholarly evidence to support their effective integration into ELT. Relying on previous empirical and theoretical studies, the article analyzes how educational innovations influence language learning outcomes and teaching practices. The review highlights educational benefits of technology-enhanced instruction, including increased learner engagement, improved language skills development, and enhanced teaching efficiency. Through analysis the study clarifies the pedagogical value of innovative technologies and emphasizes their role in building more interactive, learner-centered, and effective English language teaching and learning.

Key words: *English Language Teaching (ELT), educational efficiency, technology-enhanced instruction, learner-centered teaching, technological advancements*

In the current era of digital innovation every field is revolving by the integration of advanced technologies, fresh approaches as well as modern solutions. English Language Teaching (ELT) at this point has to adapt novel ideas of using innovative technologies for the purposes of enhancing the effectiveness of language instruction and remaining up-to-date. Moreover, the fact that every lesson-attending learner consciously or unconsciously expects to learn something new, to enrich knowledge, to clarify the abstract thoughts and most often to enjoy the experience and every teacher at the same time regardless of the subject they teach want to spend a quality work time by instructing students justifies the argument of including interesting technological advancements that improve lesson quality. To support the above-mentioned claim the example of a comparative study by Kandukoori, Kandukoori, and Wajid (2024) discovered that students using **digital learning tools**, to be more specific interactive math websites, improved their test scores much more than peers using traditional worksheets.¹ The same research on classroom technologies demonstrated that student response systems and smartphones **for learning** improved **student engagement and collaborative learning**, which are critical for learning performance. Although the study was conducted in a mathematics context, its findings are relevant to ELT, as they show the broader pedagogical potential of digital tools in enhancing learner engagement, feedback, and learning outcomes. Another empirical research study discussed the application of innovative pedagogical technologies in improving educational efficiency. Based on the results of the study, it was shown that an improvement in student motivation, and academic performance was achieved with the help of digital learning tools. The results highlighted that 85 % of students found new methods interesting, not mentioning the standardized-test results of these students being higher by 20-30% than those who were taught in traditional setting.

¹ Kandukoori, A., Kandukoori, A., & Wajid, F. (2024). *Comparative analysis of digital tools and traditional teaching methods in educational effectiveness*. arxiv. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2408.06689>

These results confirm that innovative pedagogical approaches contribute to higher effectiveness in education and help reinforce students' knowledge.¹

Regarding the psychological features the literature review shows that Richard E. Mayer in the subjects of Psychology and Educational Psychology published a book "Multimedia Learning". In his book he gave the claim that "People learn more deeply from words and pictures than from words alone."² Technological tools as mentioned above provide not only text-based content but also visuals helping the learner to gain the information with twice ease. Videos, animations, slides, pictures, gamification methods support the straightforward cognitive learning. Lawyer and philologist, Lev S. Vygotsky in his book "Mind in Society The Development of Higher Psychological Processes"³ mentions learning as an active and dynamic process not just passive reception. Using various technological tools in the learning process certainly makes students engaged and the level of passive participation decreases. Therefore, relying just on traditional teaching resources may not always produce desired outcomes. Another psychological evidence is based on the theory of Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M.⁴ where the educational technologies is said to enhance intrinsic motivation of learners by giving the lead over pace, feedback, and interaction. It supports the psychology-based idea that the motivation of students increases when they experience autonomy in addressing questions in different gamified tools, competence in being able to use technology for their own use, and relatedness in having the capability of learning certain theories through the help of educational technologies. In addition, innovative pedagogical technologies enabled learners to develop self-assessment and self-monitoring skills. Students actively participate in evaluating their own achievements, which in turn increases their sense of responsibility toward learning.

¹ Xolmatova, D. V. (2025). The use of innovative pedagogical technologies in improving educational efficiency. In *Proceedings of the Republican Scientific-Practical Conference "Modern Problems of Intelligent Systems"* (pp. 77–80). Jizzakh, Uzbekistan.

² Mayer, R. E. (2009). *Multimedia learning* (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.

³ Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Harvard University Press.

⁴ Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivations. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 25(1), 54–67

From the instructor's viewpoint there is no doubt that increased learning interest of students and achievement of desired lesson outcomes certainly makes the teacher satisfied with the teaching process. Relying on one research again a positive attitude toward the adoption and practical implementation of innovative pedagogical technologies was observed among teachers. More than 90% of them considered the opportunities to make lessons engaging and interactive through new approaches to be important (Kholmatova, 2025). According to teachers, conducting lessons using innovative methods not only enhanced students' knowledge but also contributed to the development of independent thinking and effective problem-solving skills. Educational technological tools can be the best assistant to teachers. Starting from lesson planning and content-creation, assessment and automatic grading, classroom management and organization to student engagement and interaction technology works the best if it is used appropriately. feedback and progress tracking such as learning management systems, automated assessment platforms, and AI-assisted content creation tools significantly reduce teachers' workload by streamlining lesson preparation, classroom management, and assessment processes. By using digital tools, teachers are no longer burdened with extensive paperwork.

Another positive side of using technological advancements in classroom is that this process teaches digital literacy to students especially young learners. When technological tools are integrated thoughtfully into the learning process, they can foster responsible usage habits and support academic development. By guiding students on how to use technology effectively for learning, educators help them develop digital literacy and self-regulation skills. As a result, students become more motivated to use technology as a means of acquiring knowledge rather than engaging in potentially harmful or non-educational activities. A leading academic tasked by the UK government with reviewing the effects of smartphones on teenagers has suggested "blanket bans are unrealistic and potentially detrimental".¹ This idea also supports the

¹ Orben, A. (2025, April 3). Blanket ban on teen smartphone use 'potentially detrimental', says academic. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com>

fact that young learners must use educational technologies in learning settings to have digital literacy.

In conclusion, the importance and effectiveness of technological tools in every classroom and in ELT as well can not be underestimated due to the pedagogical justifications given above. Therefore, learning the types, purposes and functional systems of modern educational technological tools has a cardinal role to play in today's digital world. Future research may further explore subject-specific applications and long-term impacts of technology integration in language education. Nonetheless, it is evident that thoughtful and informed use of innovative technologies holds a central role in shaping effective, engaging, and future-oriented English language teaching.

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